

DIRECTIONS OF STAFFING THE UZBEKISTAN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN THE SOVIET PERIOD (2ND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY)

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Abstract: the article describes the problems of the Soviet state's choice of a planned development path, formation of a "unified national economy", its management, and staffing. Also, the transformation of Uzbekistan into a huge cotton space of the Soviet state and the factors of development of industries serving the cotton industry are analyzed.

Key words: "unified national economy", collective farm, state farm, cotton farming, mechanization personnel

Science and technology development has begun to rapidly enter all spheres of society's life. It is impossible to improve any sector of the national economy without the extensive participation of technology. Great achievements were made in the field of science, technology and technology in the former USSR. After all, it is impossible to advance in any field without technology. This is directly related to improving the agriculture of Uzbekistan and providing it with excellent equipment. The war undoubtedly affected the central and western regions of the country, all war-torn regions, and pushed back their economic development for several decades. However, the consequences of war can be seen at every step even in our country where there is no war. As you know, above we discussed the fact that during the war, tractors, cars, various other equipment were taken from Uzbekistan to the front. But after the end of the war, such equipment was not returned to Uzbekistan. So, during the period before the war, agricultural machinery was introduced to a certain extent in the republic and its material base was strengthened, but after the war, we were deprived of these achievements. Now, it was necessary to fill the vacant tractor and machinery park of collective farms and state farms.

Apart from this, there were some other reasons that demanded the faster and better strengthening of the agricultural material and technical base of the republic in the late 50s and early 60s. In particular, since the mid-1950s, the development of reserves and gray lands in Uzbekistan required a much faster pace of work in this regard. Because these works, for example, the digging of canals, rivers, large ditches, the construction of irrigation and reclamation facilities, could not be carried out without modern technology. Uzbekistan needed thousands of tractors, combines, and excavators. Another reason for the demand for the development of agricultural machinery in the republic was that since the 1950s there were prospects for a wider introduction of mechanization in cotton farming, including picking cotton with the help of machines. This required the sharp development of the types of industries that produce agricultural machinery.

The Council of People's Commissars of the USSR and VKP (b) MQ of 1945 "On measures to restore and further develop cotton growing in Uzbekistan"[1], on February 2, 1946, the Council of People's Commissars of the VKP (b) MQ and the USSR Council of People's

Commissars "On measures to restore and further develop cotton growing in Uzbekistan in 1946-1953" and in February 1947 of the VKP (b) MQ of February 1947 In the decision "On measures to further improve agriculture in the post-war period"[2], he set the task of developing this branch of agriculture more strongly, strengthening organizational and political work in collective farms, and creating a basis for working with personnel in party organizations. However, in a situation where the balance in the economy is broken, large material equipment, factorial qualified personnel and other means are not enough, the Soviet regime, as always, looking out for its own interests, set Uzbekistan a difficult task to implement, including the development of cotton cultivation and the creation of cotton harvesting techniques in a short period of time. In 1945, 22,353 brigades were established in collective farms based on cotton production in Uzbekistan[3].

In the years after the war, 7% of the total funds were allocated for the agricultural production needs of Uzbekistan. During this period, programs were adopted to carry out large-scale work on the training of qualified personnel in public professions, providing agricultural enterprises with highly qualified specialists, and the main attention was paid to the increase of mechanized and technical personnel in public professions, skilled agricultural workers in the village. The reason for the importance of this situation is that as a result of the war, the composition of collective farmers and agrarian workers was significantly updated, and the composition of personnel was mainly filled with women and teenagers who did not have the necessary professional knowledge.

The decision of the Council of Ministers of the USSR on September 20, 1946 "On measures to improve the training of labor reserves and increase the number of workers trained in vocational and technical educational institutions and schools of FZT" was one of the documents defining the importance of state labor reserves[4]. Although this decision defined concrete measures to improve the work of the state labor reserves, practical tasks in the field of eliminating the shortage of labor force, this situation strengthened the artificial process of "turning" peasants into workers, but did not improve their social standard of living. The transformation of the villagers into collective farmers and agricultural workers in real life turned them into hired employees of the state and completely dependent workers. A great deal of attention was paid to the direct provision of personnel to the cotton ginning industry, because in the first five years after the war, the focus was on the improvement of cotton production, the development of mechanization and chemicalization of agriculture, and the acceleration of irrigation and melioration construction. The expected goal was to bring the gross cotton harvest to the pre-war level (1.4 million tons) in 1947, and to grow 2.6 times more cotton in 1950 than in 1945. Therefore, in 1947, 380,000 workers and specialists were trained for the cotton factories of the entire republic. In 1946-1950, 1,690,000 personnel were trained in various specialties for cotton ginning factories of the republic in technical schools, and 1,440,000 personnel were trained in Stakhanov schools for the acquisition of a second profession. During this period, according to the plan of the Soviet system, Uzbekistan became more specialized in the cultivation of agricultural products, and its place in the all-Union division of labor was determined by the level of development of cotton production. The unique structure of social production is based on this, the product processing industry and the enterprises supplying production tools for cotton growing have taken the leading place. For this reason, since 1954, the vocational and technical education system has also switched to

the training of personnel for agriculture, as a result, the training of specialists for industry has significantly decreased[5].

According to a study conducted in 1947, about 50% of the employees in the state farms of Uzbekistan had less than three years of work experience. 34.7% of the length of service of collective farm chairpersons. More than 90% of the villagers were mainly engaged in manual labor and animal labor [6]. These indicators are at a lower level in the collective farms of the republic, and the number of mechanized workers decreased during the war years. For example, in 1941, 27,888 mechanists worked on Uzbek farms, and in 1943, their number decreased to 2,775. In 1945, mechanizers increased to 7,223. But this does not mean that the number is absolutely sufficient. It should be noted that in the first years after the war, there were serious problems in training mechanics. In particular, there is no necessary material base for filling qualified mechanics and repair workers, most educational institutions have very few qualified teachers, necessary training manuals, equipment, and tools are lacking, and those that are available do not meet the requirements.

Despite these problems, state labor reserve schools and educational institutions have taken an important place in the system of training technical personnel for agricultural production processes. As a result of the implementation of the proposed measures, the number of personnel who graduated from educational institutions in the system of labor reserves sent to agriculture in 1946-1948 increased by 2.5 times. During the years 1940-1958, in educational institutions, together with more than 180,000 skilled workers, mechanizers for agriculture were trained for the national economy of the republic. This process was also significantly influenced by the establishment of correspondence education in 1949.

In order to speed up the training of personnel, the Ministry of Agriculture of Uzbekistan recommended to the heads of the MTS, cotton, livestock, breeding and grain state farms to attach apprentices to the main production workers of the workshops until March 20, 1947. Also, as a result of the use of various means of vocational training for agricultural personnel, it was determined that their number will increase significantly. In 1950-1951, 2,762 agro-zootechnical courses were organized in collective farms of the republic, state farms and other agricultural enterprises.

82,237 collective farmers and agricultural workers received training in these courses. A year later, this number reached 89,100 people. During 1951-1954, a total of 495,500 people attended three-year agro-zootechnical courses in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and 311,200 agricultural workers graduated from these courses. The number of employees of other categories of agricultural production also increased slightly. However, along with the positive achievements in the formation of agricultural personnel in public professions, there were also serious shortcomings. Despite the large number of personnel in this field, the needs of the farms for personnel in general professions, especially technical personnel, remained at a high level. In particular, there was a lack of tractor drivers, who make up a large group of mechanics.

For example, in 1953, the supply of MTS with tractor drivers was 42%[7]. In the 1950s, after the issue of expansion of all collective farms was raised by the leadership, the provision of agricultural management personnel became one of the main problems. The reason is that, according to January 1, 1946, there were a total of 1,749 highly educated specialists in Uzbekistan, including 97 reclamation workers, 95 agricultural mechanization and electrification engineers. 37% of agricultural managers belonging to the Uzbek nationality,

23% with higher education, 53% with secondary education, and 24% with primary education. Of these, 54.3% were Uzbeks among MTS leaders. In many farms, the positions of agronomists, zootechnicians, and chairpersons, specialists in agricultural production in general, were occupied by illiterate people or war veterans. The level of education of collective farm chairmen, MTS and state farm directors was low [8]. In particular, according to the data of the state survey conducted in 1947, only 89 of the 6,647 collective farm heads graduated from special higher and secondary special educational institutions, 778 people had general secondary education, and 5,780 people were included in the table of "others". In this table of "others" only the heads of collective farms with primary education were included. Of the 632 collective farm heads of Andijan region, 558 were illiterate and 66 were illiterate. However, it was difficult to expect reforms that would increase the efficiency of agriculture in the future from the leaders who were uneducated, did not have special training, and could not master modern science and technology achievements in time. Therefore, it was necessary to take strict measures to improve the expansion of information and special training of agricultural management personnel, to strengthen collective farms and state farms, MTS with qualified specialists. As a result, the Central Committee of the VKP (b) made a decision in the February 1947 plenum in the field of training of agricultural personnel, including managerial personnel[9]. In 1947, in order to improve the quality of agricultural personnel - collective farm chairmen, foremen, farm managers, accountants, and to open one- and two-year public schools in the regions and republics, as well as to establish model farms where knowledge and experience can be increased. In accordance with the decision, the Soviet of Ministers of the USSR approved the branch of the unified state schools for the training of agricultural managers. In Uzbekistan, two schools for 500 students each were opened in Tashkent and Samarkand. In two-year public schools for training agricultural managers, students were given general education as well as special knowledge about agriculture, that is, mechanization and electrification of agriculture, the basics of farming, animal husbandry, and other such lessons were taught. In 1948-1950, 740 people were trained in the two-year sections of the schools, and 960 collective farm leaders were trained in six-month courses. Graduates who completed the two-year section of the public school were awarded the title of organizer-technician and a diploma[10].

During these years, 12 technical schools trained agricultural personnel in the system of the Ministry of Agriculture of Uzbekistan. There were three agricultural institutes in Uzbekistan: agricultural institutes located in Tashkent and Samarkand and Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers. In 1954, higher agricultural educational institutions were transferred from the Ministry of Agriculture of the USSR to the Ministry of Higher Education of Uzbekistan. In 1954, the Ministry of Finance of the USSR allocated money to the Ministry of Higher Education of the USSR for the training of agricultural personnel, including the replenishment of funds from the educational experimental farms. The funds were to be spent mainly on expanding the material base of agricultural educational institutions, repairing educational buildings and dormitories. Because if the above-mentioned problems are solved, the quality of training of qualified specialists will be improved to a certain extent. At the same time, a large amount of agricultural machinery was handed over to the Ministry of Higher Education for agricultural higher educational institutions from MTS. As the material base of higher educational institutions expanded to a certain extent, the scientific potential of the specialists studying

there also increased significantly. The task of providing agriculture with specialists was assigned to agricultural higher educational institutions and technical institutes. In the academic year 1954-1955, higher educational institutions of the republic trained more than 2,500 engineers and about 1,500 other specialists of agricultural production. During 1956-1958, 3611 people received diplomas of agronomist, irrigator, engineer and other specialties. In 1954-1960, 704 engineers and technicians were sent to agriculture.

On March 25, 1955, the decision "On further strengthening of collective farms with leading personnel" was adopted. After this decision, until July 1955, it was envisaged that at least 30,000 advanced, well-trained party workers, Soviet economic workers, engineers and technicians, workers and servants, communists, as well as non-party workers should be sent to the collective farms for management work. In fact, the event was another pretext for the center's plan. The special representatives sent from the cities were not able to increase its development due to their lack of understanding of rural traditions, and were sent not "voluntarily" but under the strict demands of the leadership. Such specialists were completely ignorant of agricultural production, and among them there were those who thought of returning to the city as soon as possible. However, despite these irresponsibility, the number of urban residents sent to agriculture increased year by year. Because the purpose of the event was to send Party and Soviet workers from urban activists to the countryside and systematically inculcate the ideas of Marxism-Leninism in the rural population, to further strengthen the management of the system, and to strengthen forced labor without allowing the cadres to work according to their wishes, to distribute them to places where there is no education, and if any problems arise later, there was a policy of making themselves guilty. This event later entered history under the name of the "30 thousand" movement. It should be noted that such measures of the regime lead to the disproportion of the personnel policy, and all the damage fell on the local population.

Under the conditions of the Soviet system, the ruling policy took all possible measures to limit the national interests of local cadres. He condemned them to general equality and poverty. From the beginning, it was strictly forbidden for the population to have excess property. For example, according to archive documents, on March 28, 1947, the People's Court of the 3rd district of Andijan city brought Botirali Akhmadaliev to justice. The reason is that he refused to hand over his three head of cattle to the collective farm, slaughtered them for his own needs, took them to the market and sold them. The People's Court of Lower Chirchik District 1, Tashkent Region, Mirkhodja Kattakhodjaev, who worked as a signalman in this district, was brought to justice because he went to the market and bought 72 meters of different types of gazmol, 4 pairs of kavush, 8 glass lamps, and these goods exceeded the needs of his family. It can be seen from these small facts that the Uzbek people could not independently use their earned income. It was not possible to adequately provide social and material living conditions. Most of the villagers were not given passports in the early days in order not to run away from difficulties. The plans of the collective farm were deliberately exaggerated, and the peasants were kept firmly in debt. The intellectuals raised issues such as the harsh lifestyle in the villages, the very low wages received by farmers, and the increase in the price of cotton, but cotton planting, planning, and price determination were carried out by the center. In addition, the decision "On the development of 300,000 hectares of reserves and gray lands in Uzbekistan" adopted by the leadership in 1956 provided for a sharp increase in cotton cultivation. As a result, the development of deserts in Mirzachol, Karshi, Jizzakh,

Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, Central Fergana and the lower basin of Amudarya was accelerated and 510 thousand hectares of new land was put into use in the ninth five-year period. About 300,000 hectares of land have been developed in Mirzachol, and about 60,000 new households and state farms have been built. About 50,000 hectares of land were developed in the Jizzakh desert, and new cotton collective farms and state farms were established. However, the main population of the newly displaced people are representatives of the local nationality, and the work of settling the households and providing them with housing was in an unsatisfactory state. Social support for farms transferred to several newly assimilated districts of the republic could not cover the measures written on paper. For example, 600 families moved to Karshi deserts during the entire period of organized resettlement. Until 1989, 40 of them lived. The main reason for this was the lack of suitable jobs for the population[7]. As a result, the living conditions of the residents of a number of regions did not meet the requirements of the time and caused them to lag behind economically. It caused Uzbekistan to be lower than the level of the All-Union in terms of important indicators. For example, in 1958-1961, the average annual income per capita in the USSR was 100%, while it was 110.4% in the RSFSR, 126.4% in Estonia, 133% in Latvia, 74.7% in Turkmenistan, and 65.6% in Uzbekistan³⁵⁴. Cotton monopoly, one-sided economy, low purchase prices due to this, the material condition of the rural population in Uzbekistan was at a low level, and the value of the labor force in the agrarian sector of the republic was considered one of the lowest indicators in the Union. In the mid-1980s, a collective farmer of Uzbekistan was paid 5 rubles 88 tiyens, in Tajikistan - 6 rubles 04 tiyens, in Kyrgyzstan - 6 rubles 90 tiyens, in Turkmenistan - 7 rubles 03 tiyens, in the RSFSR - 8 rubles 03 tiyens, in Lithuania - 9 rubles 90 tiyens, in Estonia - 14 rubles 04 tiyens. Instead of solving these problems and improving the material condition of the local population, the administration looted the natural, cultural and spiritual resources of the republic and regularly transported them to the center during the implementation of the "plan".

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